

Next FOOD

EDUCATING THE NEXT GENERATION
OF PROFESSIONALS IN THE AGRIFOOD SYSTEM

D6.5: Information material for scientists and public no.2

WP6– Communication, dissemination and exploitation

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Executive summary

The purpose of the following Deliverable is to present the information material for scientists and public that has been produced and disseminated to partners, scientists and public the last 18 months following D6.4.

NextFOOD as a project relies heavily on the proper communication and engagement of the community of the agrifood and forestry sectors, as well as the respective educational field. The following document provides the blueprint for the material created and employed for informing the scientists and the public about the context of the NextFOOD project and the created educational tools that can be used to design educational systems that prepare professionals with competencies to push the green shift in our rapidly changing society.

The NextFOOD's overall strategy intends to communicate the results of the project to a multitude of audiences and engage in a two-way exchange with the interested parties. The project partners have identified the relevant target audiences and stakeholders, as well as appropriate channels to reach them which will be presented in this report.

D6.5 is covering the period from 30/10/2019 to 30/04/2021.

1 Information material for scientists & public

Information material through Project Website & platform

The NextFOOD project has developed a website and a platform to serve as the main communication, dissemination and exploitation tool. In this respect, the website and the platform have been organized and continuously re-organized and updated in such a way that will serve the specific characteristics of both the general public and the targeted audiences of the project among which are the scientists. Additionally, the website has incorporated a platform with free subscription access for the period of the project. The platform will target scientists as well as public (educators and practitioners in the field), serving as the operational and communicational tool in order to disseminate experience from cases, teaching tips and learning materials to teaching practitioners. Website (www.nextfood-project.eu)

1.1 DOE Strategy Phases

The NextFOOD's DEO strategy is based on a successive step approach which consists from four (4) different phases focusing on

1. the development of an interest network,
2. activation of participants in the project actions,
3. iterative assessment and elaboration of the produced knowledge, and finally
4. dissemination and exploitation.

1.2 Website

<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/>

Project's website in one of the many outputs of the fourth phase which as case studies advance and deliverables are concluded over the last 18 months has been updated and re organized to facilitate new needs as expressed by the consortium and the public. It has been equipped with a translation tool to allow for easier access to native languages.

Figure 1: Translation Tool

The menu in the first page has been reorganized and several categories and subcategories have been added.

Figure 2: Menu

On “deliverables and tools” users can be informed on the deliverables of each WP and download them, on the various tools that have been created (i.e audit tool for research and education – D1.2) and on the abstracts that have been created (<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/deliverables/>, <https://www.nextfood-project.eu/abstracts-2/>).

DELIVERABLES

WP1: Inventory of the skills needed for a transition to more sustainable agriculture, forestry and associated bio-value chains

D1.1 Inventory of skills and competencies

[Download it here](#)

D1.2 Audit tool for research and education

D1.3 A framework for assessing quality in education

WP2: Action research facilitation

[Translate](#) D2.1 Research protocol for NEXTFOOD case studies

Figure 3: Deliverables

NextFood has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738.

Funding: Horizon 2020, European Union
Call: Rural Renaissance – Fostering Innovation and Business Opportunities

- Practice Abstract #6: MSc. Agroecology course: Action learning in Farming and Food Systems
- Practice Abstract #7: Main practical recommendations of the University of Oradea course
- Practice Abstract #8: Small scale farmers contributing to Agroecology education at Farmers Training Centre in Ethiopia
- Practice Abstract #9: Aquaponics Project Wins Sustainable Supply Chain International Student Competition Game
- Practice Abstract #10: Action learning Agriscapes: Enhanced extension service to young farmers based on principles and practices of the Action Learning method
- Practice Abstract #11: Towards a profitable and sustainable forestry chain – Increased quality and number of micro-habitats for enhanced biodiversity
- Practice Abstract #12: Development of sustainable farming systems I+II
- Practice Abstract #13: Action learning to become a gastronome: experiential learning links theory and practice and develop students' competencies
- Practice Abstract #14: Three months certificate course in Agroecology at University of Calcutta

Figure 4: Practice Abstracts

A separate category in the menu titled “Relative projects and networking” (<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/relative-projects/>) has been created to incorporate other relative to NextFOOD EU projects with which we have initiated active collaboration or we are just interacting through mainly our relative social media. The latter has resulted to increased visits in our website.

DESIRA (Digitisation: Economic and Social Impacts in Rural Areas)

Figure 5: Relative projects and networking

The “case study” category (<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-5-action-learning-agriscapes/>) enables the user to a. get an overview of each case study and, b. leads him/her to the platform’s special menu (https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-LYRbPvUR1C98ei47xpH) where he/she can be informed with greater detail on the expected outcome of each case study, watch relative videos and be informed on material relating for example, for use case 5 to farm animal production, plant production, educational material, articles, highlights of the cases’ cycles, etc. as the cases progress and the partners upload this information material in the platform.

CASE 5.

Action learning Agriscapes: Enhanced extension service to young farmers based on principles and practices of the Action Learning method.

Get more information about Case 5 here!

Case Leader: Filippos Papadopoulos [email](#)

Case Location: American Farm School [Homepage](#)

Where: Greece

Main stakeholders involved: two networks of farmers, extension specialists, MSc students

Multi-actor approach in case: four different networks of farmers working together with extension specialists and students trained in action learning.

Expected outcome: The case is designed to facilitate the short and the longterm survival and prosperity of young farmers by familiarizing them with sustainable and competitive farming techniques and practices. The services offered are based on the model of the US university extension system. In order to engage farmers in co-creation of knowledge, we will apply the NextFOOD action learning model to these extension services. The success of this intervention will be measured by assessing the skills of farmers and advisers

Figure 6: Case study-website

The screenshot displays the NextFOOD website interface. On the left is a vertical navigation menu with options like 'Latest', 'Partners', 'Project Tasks', 'Project Info', 'Action-Learning in practice / Cases', 'News & Events', 'Toolbox', 'Non Scientific Material', and 'Other Tools'. The main content area is titled 'Case 5: Action learning Agriscapes (GR)' with a subtitle '07/02/2019 - 06. American Farm School'. Below the title is a large photograph of two people in a golden wheat field. A 'Navigate to:' button is visible above the image. Below the image, there is a 'Watch on YouTube' button. The 'Subcategories' section contains six tiles: 'Action Learning Activities' (with the NextFOOD logo), 'NUTRITION' (with an image of various fruits and vegetables), 'FARM ANIMAL REPRODUCTION' (with an image of a cow), 'ONLINE ACTION-BASED LEARNING Resources' (with an image of speech bubbles), 'CASE DEVELOPMENT REPORTS' (with a line graph), and 'ACTION-BASED ACTIVITIES PHOTOGRAPHS' (with an image of a camera lens).

Figure 7: Case study-platform

The same procedure is followed for the leaflets that have been created by the WP leaders for each case which provide information material for both scientists and public (further analysis on page 28).

Information material is also available in the website in the category titled “news & events” (<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/news/>) where users can further be led to the latest newsletters, press releases and project’s workshops and events and view relative videos and presentations also found in platform in relative sections and the project’s you tube channel.

Figure 8: News & Events

Each of the above material can be easily disseminated through the user’s fb, twitter, Instagram via the special key provided at the end of each category (<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/focus-group-meetings/>)

The **Greek Focus Group** reflects a balanced blend of different organisation types, stakeholders and expertise, providing a good representativeness of Greek food supply-chain. More specifically, it has been constituted by external stakeholders and auditors in representation of farmers, agro-food producers (e.g. fruits, meat or fish producers), standard organisation, technology providers, local authorities and institutions. The events have been co-organised and co-led by , [American Farm School](#) , [iBO / CERTH](#) , and [Green Projects](#).

During this event, the participants had the opportunity to learn more about these three innovative European programs.

Share This Story, Choose Your Platform! f t in p e

- Archives
- > April 2021
 - > March 2021
 - > February 2021
 - > January 2021
 - > December 2020
 - > November 2020
 - > September 2020
 - > August 2020
 - > July 2020
 - > April 2020

Figure 9: Special Key for fb, twitter, etc

1.3 Website Analytics

Website NextFOOD Analytics Overview – Annex 1

Website NextFOOD Analytics Acquisition Overview – Annex 2

Website NextFOOS Analytics Audience Overview – Annex 3

NextFOOD Social Media User engagement Report – Annex 7

1.4 Platform

<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/nextfood-platform/>

The NextFOOD Project website incorporates a platform with free subscription access where the current results of the project including teaching tips and learning materials is being presented.

The NextFOOD Project platform is the most powerful tool to ensure the connection of the project partners with the actual target of their work, scientists and public.

Currently in the NextFOOD project Platform has been registered 452 active users.

The knowledge-sharing platform is a technology enabler for social knowledge co-creation and innovation diffusion, thus providing the space for multi-actor action learning within communities of practice.

Having in mind the audience group and their needs the layout and the content of the platform has been updated in order to address the need and requirements of its users, in particular by adding a tool box, as well as the overall availability of platform tools. All changes were made after the requests and recommendations of the responsible project committee.

Figure 10: Register in platform

NextFOOD Platform Report can be found in Annex 4.
 NextFOOD Platform Analytics Data Acquisition Overview – Annex 5
 NextFOOD Platform Analytics Data Audience Overview – Annex 6
 NextFOOD Social Media User engagement Report – Annex 7

2 Information material through Social Media

NextFOOD has successfully utilized the major potential that social media have in reaching out and engaging audiences of the general public and the specific project stakeholders such as scientists. NextFOOD has additionally to Facebook page already created a Twitter account, an Instagram account, a LinkedIn group, a Google+ page, and a YouTube channel. All of the above are linked to the project's website and platform and presented in dissemination material to make sure that all channels are communicated to the maximum possible audience.

2.1 Facebook page

@nextfoodinnovativescienceandeducation

The last 18 months 130 apx posts have been made attracting 3.492 apx followers in total (Annex 7).

The posts can be divided into various categories including material of general interest, such as posts of other Horizon 2020 projects, or news and announcements from the EU portal and of specific interest such as news and announcements from partners, summary of all abstracts, videos related to case studies and teaching tips, events (workshops, focus groups, partners' meetings, etc.) thus providing information material for both scientists and public.

NextFood
8 Ιανουαρίου · 🌐

📅 Workshop on Gender Mainstreaming in Research and Education!

On January 18 at 11.00 to 12.30 CET, #nextfood will organize a workshop for all consortium members to present the final Gender Reference Guide and Toolbox.

Agenda... [Δείτε περισσότερα](#)

NextFood
31 Αυγούστου 2020 · 🌐

CERTIFICATE COURSE in AGROECOLOGY - Calcutta, India & Welthungerhilfe

This innovative course, in its 5th year, builds participation, observation, reflection, dialogue, visioning, communication and system thinking skills of the students in the domain of ecological agriculture and food systems. With real-life experiences, field assignments, peer learning and action-reflection based methodology, the course helps the students to prepare themselves for analysing, developing and sup... [Δείτε περισσότερα](#)

Online Certificate Course in **Agroecology**

This free certificate course will be introducing ecological agriculture and food systems through action learning sessions with practitioners and experts. The course is meant for farmer trainers, professionals and extension workers.

Interested applicants with bachelor's degree, need to apply together, at least in a group of two, from a same location to registration /institution with a letter of intent and CV by 10 September 2020 at: agroecology.cps@gmail.com. Call/WhatsApp +91 801 7069944

3 hours/day for 3 Months between September 2020 and January 2021

A certificate course offered by Welthungerhilfe & University of Calcutta, Indi

👍 21 6 κοινοποιήσεις

NextFOOD GR.LINKEDIN.COM
NextFood Project | LinkedIn
 NextFood Project | 119 followers on LinkedIn.
 Innovative Science & Education for Sustainable
 Agriculture | Educating the next generation of...

Μαρία Soumelidou, Katerina Dourvanaki και 3 ακόμη

Μου αρέσει! Σχόλιο Κοινοποίηση

Γράψτε ένα σχόλιο...

NextFood
 5 Φεβρουαρίου ·

Get access to NextFood's experience! Sign in and subscribe to our Educational Platform: <https://lnkd.in/d2gF5fc> ✓
 Watch the video on how to benefit from NextFOOD Platform: <https://lnkd.in/e5-C6cf> ✓

#nextfoodproject #horizon2020 #foodsystem #argifood #forestry #agroecology #farming #farm #agriscap #agritech #agrotechnology #research #innovative #sustainability #organicfood

NextFood
 6 Ιουνίου 2020 ·

It was a pleasure for the [American Farm School](#) of Thessaloniki to host NextFOOD Partners E-Meeting.

Having gone through a meaningful common course during the implementation of the project, we had the chance to meet again, look back at our achievements, delve into current issues, review our goals and set out for new ones. We shared ideas and thoughts and participated in fruitful discussions so that we all advanced our knowledge.

Thank you all for your participation!... [Δείτε περισσότερα](#)

NextFood
19 Απριλίου στις 4:04 μ.μ.

Synergy among #RUBIZMO and #NextFOOD project

The aim of the meeting was the explore the opportunities for cooperation among the two Horizon projects in terms of exchange of good practices, promotion of deliverables and interaction in the scientific implementation of their work.

RUBIZMO is a European initiative working to foster sustainable growth and job creation in rural areas by discovering the vital ingredients for developing entrepreneurship and successful business mode... [Δείτε περισσότερα](#)

15 Panos Remoundos, Εύη Χατζή και 7 ακόμη 1 κοινοποίηση

NextFood
12 Μαρτίου

2 digital meetings with local stakeholders and agricultural producers presenting the current stage of development of the #NextFOOD project.

A Agronutritional Cooperation Region Central Macedonia/ACRCM had successfully organized two digital meetings with local stakeholders and agricultural producers in order to promote and present the current stage of development of the NextFOOD project. Specifically, AC RCM coordinated 2.5-hour meeting at 23rd of February 2021 with 15 loca... [Δείτε περισσότερα](#)

15 2 κοινοποιήσεις

NextFood
8 Μαρτίου

FoodSafety4EU

8 Μαρτίου

Women will lead the transformation of the European Food Safety System of the future #FoodSafety4EU project, conceived to ease such change, has women at its c... [Δείτε περισσότερα](#)

15 Katerina Dourvanaki και 6 ακόμη 1 κοινοποίηση

NextFood
12 Απριλίου στις 12:47 μ.μ.

The study of sustainable agrifood systems through action learning.

Video Action LearningDEF

15 Katerina Dourvanaki και 4 ακόμη 1 κοινοποίηση

NextFood
12 Μαρτίου · 🌐

Τι είναι το NextFood Project ?
 Το έργο αφορά ένα νέο μοντέλο παροχής γεωργικών γνώσεων με βιωματική μάθηση/action learning model, το οποίο δίνει έμφαση στη γνώση των αγροτών και στη σημασία της δημιουργίας συνεργειών μεταξύ όλων των εμπλεκόμενων παραγόντων του γεωργικού τομέα, ώστε να τονιστεί η αειφορική διάσταση στην οποία πρέπει να στραφεί η αγροτική παραγωγή.
 Στο πλαίσιο του έργου NEXTFOOD θα εφαρμοστούν δώδεκα case studies με σκοπό την ενσωμάτωση του action learning model... [Δείτε περισσότερα](#)

YOUTUBE.COM ✓
NextFOOD Presentation in GREEK
 Το έργο αφορά ένα νέο μοντέλο παροχής γεωργικών γνώσεων μ...

NextFOOD
 PLATFORM

Find all the latest models, teaching tips and lessons-learned from the NextFOOD case studies.

GET ACCESS TO NEXTFOOD'S EXPERIENCE.

A useful tool for:
 TEACHING PRACTITIONERS
 ADVISERS
 STUDENTS

Figure 11: Various types of posts in facebook

2.2 Instagram Account (NextFOOD_H2020)

The NextFOOD Instagram account is being utilized to reach out to younger audiences and has been based primarily in visual communication tools. Partners facilitating case studies were encouraged to upload photos, short videos, practices etc. that the project engages with, mainly of the same content as the facebook posts. Current followers amount to 304 apx. (annex 7).

Figure 12: Various types of posts in Instagram

2.3 Twitter Account (@NextFOOD_H2020)

The NextFOOD twitter page has been utilized to communicate and disseminate (audio)-visual material, links for public deliverables, news and announcements concerning the actions and outcomes/results of the project, though its main focus would be to disseminate activities while they take place. There are currently 178 followers.

Figure 13: Twitts

2.4 LinkedIn page

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/nextfood-project/>

The LinkedIn page has been developed and currently WP6 leader is in the process of disseminating within the project and as well as to the identified external stakeholders and target groups including of course scientists and the public.

Figure 14: The LinkedIn page of the NextFOOD project

All stakeholders identified and engaged in local actions will be encouraged to become part of the NextFOOD LinkedIn project in order to develop a network of actors that are more interested in specialized information such as about the results and outcomes of the case studies, scientific publications etc. All members of the LinkedIn groups will be

managed and approved by the WP6 leader who is the group administrator. The WP6 leader will also have the responsibility for the account's editorial control, which can be overruled by the project leader and the managing committee.

For detailed information please see Annex 8: Nextfood LinkedIn Report
For statistics – Annex 9: Nextfood LinkedIn posts' Statistics

Figure 15: LinkedIn post

3 Audio-visual material – YouTube channel

https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCEjsZeXhtM_S3kju-iWLUww/videos

The YouTube page has been developed and already hosts 30 videos. The page hosts a short promotional animated video clip about the project, short promotional and tutorial videos about the project platform and how to use it, videos presenting different case studies, videos about the project activities, events, focus groups, meetings, presentations etc., as well the Zenodo Tutorial video.

3.1 Tutorial Video on NextFOOD platform

<https://youtu.be/gQf79XvibS8>

In order to ensure the correct use of the platform but also to maximize its impact, a 5-minute duration tutorial video has been created with explanations on how to use the platform and its tools and which are its main services.

Figure 16: The Tutorial video on the use of the NextFOOD platform

Furthermore, a video spot was also created in order to disseminate the platform over the social media and increase the awareness raising impact. (<https://youtu.be/1INpM50PsY4>)

Figure 17: The video spot on the NextFOOD platform.

3.2 Zenodo Tutorial video

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0aNK9EfnZM8>

In order to facilitate the uploading of documents and files created during the course of our project and the systematic recording of their corresponding metadata to Zenodo, a tutorial video has been created.

Figure 18: The tutorial video providing guidelines for the uploading process for the zenodo repository

3.3 Animation clip

https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCEjsZeXhtM_S3kju-iWLUww

WP6 team members strongly shared the belief that the overall aim of NextFOOD to generate an innovative European science and education roadmap for sustainable agriculture along the value chain will be better communicated to the stakeholders and the society in general, through an almost 2 min animation clip. Its makers wanted to concentrate in those two minutes the diversity in knowledge and the project's participants who represent the whole chain from field to shelf in 4 continents depicting the overall aim of NextFOOD project and the challenges that the above-mentioned global changes pose to our generation. It was not an easy task but the results justified the team's efforts. This video has been translated in all our partner's native language.

Figure 19: The animation clip

3.4 Six (6) videos on the shift of focus in agroecology education and the five core competencies

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dFt7qpkNlyo>

Figure 20: Videos on the five core competencies (NMBU)

3.5 Video on Gender Sensitive Communication

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-v7sV6tuQ6s>

"Exclusive: Google releases 53 gender fluid emojis!"

<https://www.fastcompany.com/90343461/google-releases-gender-fluid-emoji> (2019)

Figure 21: Video on Gender-Sensitive Communication

3.6 Video on the experience of CHIEAMBari students on the study of Sustainable Agrifood Systems through Action Learning

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cGIMqjTnWWs&t=1s>

The results of Action Learning activities carried out by the CIHEAMBari Master students on Mediterranean Organic Agriculture in the Alto Salento Local Action Group (LAG) territory, which aimed at developing their skills and competencies to work for sustainable agrifood systems.

Figure 22: Video on the experience of CHIEAMBari students on the study of Sustainable Agrifood Systems through Action Learning

3.7 A series of videos presenting Case Studies 1- 12 and various workshops

https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCEjsZeXhtM_S3kju-iWLUww/videos

Figure 23: videos on Case Studies and workshops

4 Newsletters

<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/category/newsletters/>
<https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/categories/-LzH2g0L-XekIraPGICr>

Newsletters provide all relevant information about the project and in particular news about actions and outputs, news concerning education and training with the project, and last but not least news about workshops, events and conferences.

Newsletter editorial board created seven issues of NextFOOD Internal Newsletters from October 2019 until March 2021.

The first four issues were published on a monthly basis; since May 2020, every three months.

We presented each issue on the project website platform.nextfood-project.eu, in category: Partners Only - Internal Newsletter. We have also been sending each issue to partners by mail. The last two issues were presented to subscribers as mail communication and also we have from March MailChimp for present newsletters to the general public.

An option for registering to NextFOOD newsletter is available on the website.

Figure 24: Newsletter registration option

Figure 25: Newsletter Issue 7/2021 as viewed on mobile phone

Annex 10: NextFOOD Newsletter 7th Mailchimp

Annex 11: NextFOOD Mailchimp Report

5 Press Releases

https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-L_D-TanVLyqEyyqkh-b

Being the main communication medium to mass media, with regards to the project activities, press releases have been scheduled so as to coincide with important events or project milestones include information either concerning a future event or results achieved in by the project. Their wording and focus was and will be accordingly adapted avoiding any use of specialized terms and/or jargon to ensure accessibility not only to scientists but to the general public as well.

Since 30/10/2019 6 press releases on a local level have been issued and disseminated by ACRCM-AFS (11.11.2019, 05.02.2020, 10.03.2021, 11.03.2021, 16.03.2021, 16.04.2021).

Press Releases can be found in our website (<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/news/> & <https://www.nextfood-project.eu/category/press-releases/>) and platform (https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/categories/-LzH20iE5rn_Zepz_84K).

Figure 26: Press Releases-website

Figure 27: Press Releases-platform

Figure 28: Press Releases- platform

6 Leaflets

Due to Covid19 all leaflets were created in an electronic form both as a printable pdf but also as a flipbook, providing information material on each case study. A special “area” in the site in each case has been created to host these flipbooks and a button to “guide” the user to the platform and to the relative subcategory titled “Action Learning Activities”. The public can thus be informed on the action learning activities or other actions that have taken place within the context of each case study. The template for creating such leaflets has been distributed to all case leaders.

Figure 29 Example of leaflet of case 5

[\(https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-5-action-learning-agriscapes/\)](https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-5-action-learning-agriscapes/)

Navigate to:

Action Learning Activities

Located in:

- Action-Learning in practice / Cases/Case studies/Case 5: Action learning Agriscapes (GR)
- Action-Learning in practice / Cases

Articles

The Transect Walk	TASK 4.2: IDENTIFICATION OF STRATEGIES FOR IMPROVEMENTS	Biodynamic course
MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH FOR ACTION LEARNING ACTIVITIES	Certificate Course on Agroecology and Action Research-Kerala	MEET THE FARMER

Figure 30: Platform – Action Learning Activities (for various case studies)
https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-MXkuyaAwRnYtnLI4UGF

Navigate to:

MEET THE FARMER

Located in:

- Action-Learning in practice / Cases/Case studies/Case 5: Action learning Agriscapes (GR)
- Action-Learning in practice / Cases/Case studies/Case 5: Action learning Agriscapes (GR)/Action Learning Activities
- Action-Learning in practice / Cases/Action Learning Activities

Related partners:

- 06. American Farm School

Case 5- Action learning Agriscapes

Attachments

 Case 5 _MEET THE FARMER.pdf
[Download](#)

Comments

Enter a comment... [Post](#)

Figure 31: Example of case 5 as a pdf in platform
https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-MXkvfQM6u-b_IDirFGu

7 EIP – AGRI abstracts

https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-LwYMFdy35tWzlpXKxe1

So far, 47 abstracts have been developed and disseminated through our platform providing visitors with information on a wide range of interesting topics. The resulting innovative knowledge is broader disseminated via relevant posts on our facebook page where the visitor can be informed on outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Figure 32: The Facebook page of PA regarding Case 8

-systems-by-bringing-in-agroecological
-approach-through-action-learning/
Also, read the practice abstract on "Farmers as teachers of agroecology"
<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/nextfood-pa22.pdf>
#agroecology #farmers #actionresearch #actionlearning

Figure 33: The Facebook page of PA regarding Case 9

8 Publications

All publications can be found both in Zenodo and NextFood platform (https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/categories/-Lca4vdOTMeBD2_hDXOG). ;

Zenodo is an open-access repository that allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, and any other research related digital artifacts and exposes them to interested parties.

So far the following two publications took place:

1. Chrysanthi Charatsari, Håkan Jönsson and Philip Papadopoulos, Looking for the missing link: The multiple meanings of sustainability in agricultural knowledge and information systems presented at the “24th European Seminar on Extension and Education”
2. Geir Lieblein, Tor Arvid Breland, Anna Marie Nicolaysen, Charles Francis, Åsmund Legreid, Lutgart Lenaerts, Edvin Østergaard, Martin Melin, Aristotle revisited – Educating the next generation of professionals for a green shift in the agrifood system (the NEXTFOOD project), 2nd Agroecology Europe Forum, Heraklion, Crete, 26-28 September 2019

Below are two publications which are ongoing:

1. WP4 (Task 4.1): Sirri R. *, Kurtsal Y. *, Fioravanti M.L., De Cesare A., Manfreda G., Luppi E., Pacetti E., Viaggi D. How do educational policies meet the needs of a changing agrifood and forestry sector towards sustainability?
2. WP1 (Focus groups): Rastorgueva N*., Sirri R., Fioravanti M., Viaggi D., Madžarić S., Belsanti V., Pugliese P., Migliorini P. Human capital and required skills for sustainable agricultural development: Italian case.ve ve

9 Nonscientific articles

<https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/categories/-MO1Q6ORMPzBnumYKDMw>

Figure 34: Non-scientific articles

Interesting articles based on case 5 and in regard to gender sensitive communication and have been edited in the following links:

https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-MSmWM9qokU7zaokYD2m

https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-MSmWpX1HDu28OfxVF5f

https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-MQR4fNcyG_WTf0_uTOi

10 Information on case studies

When users navigate to each case study in the platform, apart from general information on the particular case, he/she can find relevant interest material coming from this case. For example, in case 5: https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-LYRbPvUR1C98ei47xpH

Figure 35: Other material for scientists and public regarding case 5

11 Toolbox and other tools

<https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/categories/-M3PtoEIFOporsIH9aiW>

11.1 Toolbox

The toolbox has been developed to support teaching practitioners in successfully implementing education in line with the Nextfood approach. The toolbox will support teachers at any level of the education system (high school, vocational training & university), as well as extension specialists devoted to experiential learning

approaches. It is intended for courses and programs in the area of sustainable agrifood- and forestry systems, but the methods and models are not content-specific and can be applied in a variety of educational settings.

Figure 36: Toolbox-Platform

More about the background of the toolbox, can be found in Deliverable D3.2 "A toolbox for teaching practitioners" in the "Publications" tab of the platform. (<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/deliverables/>)

WP3: Future curriculum, education and training system

+ D3.1 Review report of educational approaches

+ D3.2 A toolbox for teaching practitioners

- D3.3 Report on educational strategy, year 1

Download it here

+ D3.4 Report on educational strategy, year 2

+ D3.5 Report on educational strategy, year 3

+ D3.6 Report on educational strategy, year 4

Figure 37:D3.2

11.2 Other tools

https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/categories/-MQRAIZ_J9VgTPW0aGOM

Figure 38: Other Tools – Platform

Special tools that can be used by the public and scientists as well can be presented in this special “area” in NextFOOD platform.

So far, such interesting material has been developed and provide guidelines on gender-sensitive language making the use of gender-sensitive communication a formal requirement in every document produced and word spoken in EU.

Figure 39: Other Tools – Platform

NEXT FOOD PLATFORM:
Reporting from November 2019 to April 2021

Annex 1 Website NextFOOD Analytics Overview

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738

The present Deliverable reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Overview

All Users
100.00% Page Views

1 Oct 2018 - 18 Apr 2021

Overview

Page Views

Page Views 42,325	Unique Page Views 35,208	Avg. Time on Page 00:01:36	Bounce Rate 69.30%	% Exit 51.70%
-----------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------------------	------------------------------	-------------------------

Page	Page Views	% Page Views
1. /	13,987	33.05%
2. /bot-traffic.xyz	5,040	11.91%
3. /nextfood-platform/	2,386	5.64%
4. /case-studies/	1,693	4.00%
5. /about-2/	1,692	4.00%
6. /consortium/	1,587	3.75%
7. /deliverables/	1,326	3.13%
8. /news/	1,135	2.68%
9. /work-packages/	662	1.56%
10. /contact/	612	1.45%

NEXT FOOD PLATFORM:
Reporting from November 2019 to April 2021

Annex 2 Website NextFOOD Analytics Acquisition Overview

Acquisition Overview

1 Oct 2018 - 18 Apr 2021

All Users
 100.00% Users

Primary Dimension:

Conversion:

Top Channels

All Goals

[Edit Channel Grouping](#)

Top Channels

Users

Conversions

Acquisition

Behaviour

	Users	New Users	Sessions	Bounce Rate	Pages/Ses...	Avg. Session Duration
	13,397	13,413	21,904	69.30%	1.93	00:01:29
1 Direct	5,809	<div style="width: 43%;"></div>		77.23%	<div style="width: 77%;"></div>	
2 Organic Search	5,582	<div style="width: 41%;"></div>		59.23%	<div style="width: 59%;"></div>	
3 Referral	2,436	<div style="width: 18%;"></div>		79.17%	<div style="width: 79%;"></div>	
4 Social	736	<div style="width: 5%;"></div>		59.66%	<div style="width: 59%;"></div>	
5 Email	42	<div style="width: 0%;"></div>		47.95%	<div style="width: 47%;"></div>	

Conversions

Set up a goal.

To see outcome metrics, define one or more goals.

[GET STARTED](#)

To see all 5 Channels click [here](#).

NEXT FOOD PLATFORM:
Reporting from November 2019 to April 2021

Annex 3 Website NextFOOF Analytics Audience Overview

Audience Overview

All Users
 100.00% Users

1 Oct 2018 - 18 Apr 2021

Overview

Users 13,397	New Users 13,413	Sessions 21,904
Number of Sessions per User 1.63	Page Views 42,325	Pages/Session 1.93
Avg. Session Duration 00:01:29	Bounce Rate 69.30%	

■ New Visitor ■ Returning Visitor

Language	Users	% Users
1. en-us	6,449	48.08%
2. en-gb	1,168	8.71%
3. el-gr	867	6.46%
4. it-it	674	5.02%
5. es-es	352	2.62%
6. da-dk	255	1.90%
7. fr-fr	253	1.89%
8. sv-se	247	1.84%
9. zh-cn	211	1.57%
10. de-de	178	1.33%

NEXT FOOD PLATFORM:
Reporting from November 2019 to April 2021
Annex 4 NEXT FOOD PLATFORM

INFORMATION MATERIAL THROUGH

NEXT FOOD PLATFORM:

Reporting from November 2019 to April 2021

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738

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Knowledge Bank of NEXTFOOD project

The [Next Food Project website](#) incorporates a platform with free subscription access where the current results of the project including teaching tips and learning materials is being presented for teaching practitioners in the field of agrifood and forestry and other targeted audience.

All partners engaged on spreading legal content through transparency and responsible behavior and to protect the core values.

The [NEXT Food Project platform](#) is the most powerful tool to ensure the connection of the project partners with the actual target of their work. It includes comprehensive information about the project activities, partnership, case studies and news from each one partner country. In figures, the platform contains the following information:

20 deliverables

35 practical abstracts

12 case studies

29 articles on studies, news and events, action learning activities, courses

8 press releases

3 nonscientific materials

1 tool for gender sensitive information

*** Detailed description of 8 WPs of the project**

*** Detailed description of 19 project partners**

1 video of the project and 2 about the platform

*** NextFOOD Toolbox**

*** Admins user Manual of the platform, banner,**

In order to ensure the correct use of the platform but also to maximize its impact, a **5-minute duration tutorial video** was created with explanations on how to use the platform and its tools and which are its main services.

Furthermore, [a video spot](#) was produced in order to disseminate the platform over the social media and increase the awareness raising impact.

Currently in the platform had been registered 452 active users.

The knowledge-sharing platform is a technology enabler for social knowledge co-creation and innovation diffusion, thus providing the space for multi-actor action learning within communities of practice.

The on-line platform is an operational and communicational tool in order to disseminate experience from:

- Case study reports
- Models
- Teaching tips
- Lessons-learned
- MSc Theses
- Best Practices Abstracts
- Event subscription
- Project calendar

SIGN IN: <https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/>

The **MENU** of NextFOOD Platform was reconstructed in February of 2020.

Old menu of the Platform

New menu of the Platform

- Manage Users
- Latest
- Partners
- Project Tasks
-
- + ADD NEW
- Work packages
- Case studies
- Press Releases
- Events
- Publications
- Gallery
- Teaching tips
- Templates
- Newsletters
- Deliverables
- Abstracts

- Latest
- Partners Info
- Project Info
- Action learning in Practice
- News & Events
- Publications
- Partners only

The new main categories will include the below subcategories:

Partners info

Project Info

- Work Packages
- Deliverables / Milestones
- Abstracts
- Project tasks

Action learning in practice / cases

- Toolbox & teaching tips
- Case Study 1
- Case Study 2
- Case Study 3
-CS 12

Latest News & Events

- Press releases
- Newsletter
- Events

Publications

- Abstracts
- Deliverables

Partners only

- Templates
- Internal newsletter
- Contact info

The **final MENU** of the NextFOOD Platform was reconstructed in April 2021 and includes the following additions:

- Projects Tasks
- Abstracts
- Non-scientific materials
- Toolbox
- Other tools

The last part of this Platform is the Toolbox

The toolbox has been developed to support teaching practitioners in successfully implementing education in line with the Nextfood approach. The toolbox will support teachers at any level of the education system (high school, vocational training & university), as well as extension specialists devoted to experiential learning approaches. It is intended for courses and programs in the area of sustainable agrifood- and forestry systems, but the methods and models are not content-specific and can be applied in a variety of educational settings.

NEXT FOOD PLATFORM:
Reporting from November 2019 to April 2021

Annex 5 NextFOOD Platform Analytics Data Acquisition
Overview

Acquisition Overview

1 Oct 2018 - 18 Apr 2021

All Users
100.00% Users

Primary Dimension:

Conversion:

Top Channels

All Goals

[Edit Channel Grouping](#)

Top Channels

Users

Conversions

Acquisition

Behaviour

	Users ↓	New Users ↓	Sessions ↓	Bounce Rate ↓	Pages/Ses... ↓	Avg. Session Duration ↓
	1,071	1,078	2,152	75.70%	1.59	00:02:06
1 Direct	711	<div style="width: 66%"></div>		74.76%	<div style="width: 66%"></div>	
2 Social	201	<div style="width: 19%"></div>		74.19%	<div style="width: 66%"></div>	
3 Referral	120	<div style="width: 11%"></div>		89.81%	<div style="width: 66%"></div>	
4 Organic Search	51	<div style="width: 5%"></div>		74.04%	<div style="width: 66%"></div>	
5 Email	9	<div style="width: 0%"></div>		66.67%	<div style="width: 66%"></div>	

Conversions

Set up a goal.

To see outcome metrics, define one or more goals.

[GET STARTED](#)

To see all 5 Channels click [here](#).

NEXT FOOD PLATFORM:
Reporting from November 2019 to April 2021

Annex 6 NextFOOD Platform analytics Data Audience
Overview

Audience Overview

1 Oct 2018 - 18 Apr 2021

All Users
100.00% Users

Overview

■ New Visitor ■ Returning Visitor

Language	Users	% Users
1. el-gr	328	30.29%
2. en-us	263	24.28%
3. en-gb	87	8.03%
4. zh-cn	78	7.20%
5. el	50	4.62%
6. it-it	50	4.62%
7. sv-se	28	2.59%
8. es-es	19	1.75%
9. da-dk	13	1.20%
10. fr-fr	12	1.11%

NEXT FOOD PLATFORM:
Reporting from November 2019 to April 2021

Annex 7 NextFOOD Social Media User Engagement Report

USER ENGAGEMENT REPORT

PERIOD

01/10/2018 - 20/04/2021

WEBSITE VISITS

21.904

YOUTUBE CHANNEL

33

LINKEDIN

312

INSTAGRAM
FOLLOWERS

302

FACEBOOK
FOLLOWERS

3.492

TWITTER
FOLLOWERS

178

PLATFORM
STATS

452 Subscribers
2.152 page views

NEXT FOOD PLATFORM:
Reporting from November 2019 to April 2021

Annex 8 NextFOOD LinkedIn Report

Next FOOD

EDUCATING THE NEXT GENERATION
OF PROFESSIONALS IN THE AGRIFOOD SYSTEM

2021

LinkedIn Report

NEXT FOOD PROJECT

STATISTIC INFORMATION FOR THE PERIOD 10/20 -04/21

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738

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The LinkedIn account of the project NEXT Food was created at 20/10/2020.

The account is available here: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/69232587/admin/>

For this period, it had achieved the following main indicators:

- **289 followers**
- **114 page views**
- **78 reaction**
- **Published 26 posts with impression of 3.828 people and received 143 likes.**
- **The average click rate is about 2.4 %**

Below you can find more detailed information about the tool.

Visitors' Metrics (for the period 20/10-13/04/2021): 114 page views

Visitor demographics

Time range: Mar 27, 2021 - Apr 10, 2021

Top job functions

Job Function	Visitors	% of Visitors
Program and Project Management	13	12%
Education	4	
Business Development	3	8%
Operations	2	4%
Arts and Design	1	4%
Media and Communication	1	4%
Research	1	4%

Update Analytics (for the period 20/10-13/04/2021): 78 reactions

Followers (for the period 20/10-13/04/2021): 289 followers

Top locations

Location	Followers	% of Followers
Rome Area, Italy	18	11.18%
Brussels Area, Belgium	8	4.97%
Bologna Area, Italy	7	4.35%
Istanbul, Turkey	4	2.48%
Lausanne Area, Switzerland	4	2.48%
Austria area	4	2.48%
Barcelona Area, Spain	3	1.86%
Bari Area, Italy	3	1.86%
Paris Area, France	3	1.86%
Copenhagen Area, Capital Region, ...	3	1.86%

Posts (for the period 20/10-13/04/2021): 26 posts

Pos t	Impressions	Reactions	Click-through rate	Comments	Shares	Clicks	Engagement rate
1	139	6	4.32%	0	1	6	9.35%
2	149	10	1.34%	0	1	2	8.72%
3	140	7	2.14%	0	0	3	7.14%

4	245	7	4.49%	0	2	11	8.16%
5	211	11	4.74%	0	2	10	10.90%
6	242	7	4.96%	0	0	12	7.85%
7	154	5	1.95%	0	0	3	5.19%
8	110	3	9.09%	0	0	10	11.82%
9	107	4	0.93%	0	0	1	4.67%
10	95	3	4.21%	0	0	4	7.37%
11	131	5	0.76%	0	0	1	4.58%
12	192	6	2.60%	0	0	5	5.73%
13	107	5	2.80%	0	0	3	7.48%
14	97	2	0.00%	0	0	0	2.06%
15	85	3	1.18%	0	0	1	4.71%
16	150	6	0.67%	0	0	1	4.67%
17	134	5	1.49%	0	1	2	5.97%
18	236	7	2.12%	0	1	5	5.51%
19	195	10	2.05%	0	1	4	7.69%
20	107	4	0.00%	0	0	0	3.74%
21	64	3	1.56%	0	0	1	6.25%
22	88	3	1.14%	1	0	1	5.68%
23	104	6	3.85%	0	0	4	9.62%
24	58	3	1.72%	0	0	1	6.90%
25	47	4	0.00%	0	0	0	8.51%
26	441	8	2.04%	0	2	9	4.31%

Posts

Posted by Lena Mouratidou • 10/20/2020

NextFood Project
285 followers
6mo •

<https://lnkd.in/dpztXDJ>

1

6

Like Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 139 Impressions Hide stats

Organic stats

Targeted to: All followers

139	6	4.32%
Impressions	Reactions	Click-through rate
0	1	6
Comments	Share	Clicks
9.35% Engagement rate		

Analytics Activity

Posted by Lena Mouratidou • 11/16/2020

NextFood Project
285 followers
5mo • Edited •

2

<https://lnkd.in/dmfMsU4>
Funding: Horizon 2020, European Union
Call: Rural Renaissance – Fostering Innovation and Business Opportunities
Topic: RUR-13-2017 Building a future science and education system fit to deliver to practice
Grant agreement: No 771738
Coordinator: Dr Martin Melin, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Alnarp, Sweden
Financial project manager: Christer Borglin, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Alnarp, Sweden
Duration: May 2018 to May 2022
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738. The present Deliverable reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Credit:
Perspectives by Kevin MacLeod
Link: <https://lnkd.in/fCe945u...>
License: <https://lnkd.in/gT9HGyF...>

Analytics Activity

NextFOOD Project
youtube.com

10

Like Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 149 Impressions Hide stats

Organic stats

Targeted to: All followers

149	10	1.34%
Impressions	Reactions	Click-through rate

Posted by Lena Mouratidou • 11/16/2020

NextFood Project
285 followers
5mo •

3

Workshop for the "Identification of strategies for improving the educational policy network".

...see more

7

7

Like Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 140 Impressions

Hide stats

Organic stats

Targeted to: All followers

140 Impressions	7 Reactions	2.14% Click-through rate
-----------------	-------------	--------------------------

0 Comments	0 Shares	3 Clicks
------------	----------	----------

7.14% Engagement rate

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 1/30/2021

NextFood Project
285 followers
2mo •

4

Focus Group meetings

Between 18 and 22 December, three virtual Focus Group meetings were organised in the spirit of co-creation and participation. These events were also the occasion of #NextFOOD to join effort with two other European projects, #MEDFoodTTHubs and #InoFA as well as a pool of recognised experts engaged in the agro-food and traceability sectors.

Each of the three initiatives was interested to exchange views in the context of the development of innovative solutions in the field of agro-food supply chain. Hence, the decision to join forces and share common views with our stakeholders.

The Greek Focus Group reflects a balanced blend of different organisation types, stakeholders and expertise, providing a good representativeness of Greek food supply-chain.

More specifically, it has been constituted by external stakeholders and auditors in representation of farmers, agro-food producers (e.g. fruits, meat or fish producers), standard organisation, technology providers, local authorities and institutions.

The events have been co-organised and co-led by , American Farm School , iBO / CERTH , and Green Projects.

During this event, the participants had the opportunity to learn more about these three innovative European programs.

#agro #sustainability #innovation

7

Like Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 245 Impressions

Hide stats

Organic stats

Targeted to: All followers

245 Impressions	7 Reactions	4.49% Click-through rate
-----------------	-------------	--------------------------

0 Comments	2 Shares	11 Clicks
------------	----------	-----------

8.16% Engagement rate

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738

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Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 2/3/2021

NextFood Project
285 followers
2mo •

5

Get access to NextFood's experience!
Sign in and subscribe to our Educational Platform:
<https://lnkd.in/d2gF5fc>

Watch the video on how to benefit from NextFOOD Platform:
<https://lnkd.in/e5-C6cf>

#nextfoodproject #horizon2020 #foodsystem #argifood #forestry #agroecology
#farming #farm #agriscap #agritech #agrotechnology #research #innovative
#sustainability #organicfood

Tutorial video of NextFOOD Platform
youtube.com

11

Like Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 211 Impressions

Organic stats
Targeted to: All followers

211 Impressions	11 Reactions	4.74% Click-through rate
0 Comments	2 Shares	10 Clicks
10.9% Engagement rate		

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 2/7/2021

NextFood Project
285 followers
2mo •

6

On the 26th of January Nextfood met with the [Newbie.eu](#) team to share knowledge and discuss possible synergies. NEWBIE is an EIP-AGRI thematic network on new entrants into farming, with focus on new business models and capacity building for this target group. At the meeting, snapshots of the two projects were presented followed by a discussion on possible collaboration and synergies. Interestingly, the same competences identified as necessary among new entrants in agriculture were similar to the competence profile of the Nextfood inventory of skills. Several touchpoints exist between the two projects, e.g. the development of tools as well new educational modules, which give reason for further collaboration between the two projects. For more information about NEWBIE, please visit their excellent homepage:
<https://lnkd.in/eKfAv4C>.

#nextfoodproject #horizon2020 #foodsystem #argifood #forestry #agroecology
#farming #farm #agriscap #agritech #agrotechnology #research #innovative
#sustainability #organicfood

7

Like Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 242 Impressions

Organic stats
Targeted to: All followers

242 Impressions	7 Reactions	4.96% Click-through rate
0 Comments	0 Shares	12 Clicks
7.85% Engagement rate		

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 2/19/2021 • Boost unavailable ⓘ

NextFood Project
285 followers
1mo • Edited • ⚙️

7

The competition series is one of the cases of Nextfood Project which promotes innovative education for sustainable agriculture.

#horizon2020 #agrifood #agroecology #innovations #biodiversity

ISEKI-Food Association
610 followers
1mo • ⚙️

FoodFactory-4-Us Final Virtual Conference on Valorizing Food Biodiversity

📅 Thursday 18 February at 13:00 CET. ...see more

5

👍 Like 💬 Comment

NextFood Project Add a comment...

Organic impressions: 154 Impressions

Organic stats ⓘ

Targeted to: All followers

154 Impressions	5 Reactions	1.95% Click-through rate
0 Comments	0 Shares	3 Clicks
5.19% Engagement rate		

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 2/23/2021

NextFood Project
285 followers
1mo • Edited • ⚙️

8

The Commission presents the results of a study on the expected economic effects by 2030 of ongoing and upcoming trade negotiations on the EU agricultural sector. Moreover, it provides insights on the evolution of supply, demand, and farm-gate prices for the most relevant EU agricultural commodity markets.

Link to the study: <https://lnkd.in/eZ33CTC>

#study #agroevolution #farms #prices #EUFarmers #foodproducers

3

3

Thanks for posting... In my opinion... What about...

👍 Like 💬 Comment

NextFood Project Add a comment...

Organic impressions: 110 Impressions

Organic stats ⓘ

Targeted to: All followers

110 Impressions	3 Reactions	9.09% Click-through rate
0 Comments	0 Shares	10 Clicks
11.82% Engagement rate		

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NextFood Project
285 followers
1mo • 🌐

9

Commission publishes study on information measures under the common agricultural policy 📄

...see more

Evaluation support study on the information policy on the Common Agricultural Policy : final report.
op.europa.eu • 1 min read

4

Thank you for... This is a... I'm curious... Thanks for posting >

Like Comment

Add a comment... 🗨️ 📷

Organic impressions: 100 Impressions Hide stats ^

Organic stats ⓘ

Targeted to: All followers

100 Impressions	4 Reactions	1% Click-through rate
0 Comments	0 Shares	1 Click
5%		

NextFood Project
285 followers
1mo • 🌐

10

Book the date! Interesting and inspiring conference by ISEKI Food Association!

ISEKI-Food Association
610 followers
1mo • 🌐

🌿 The Urban Jungle is calling! 🌿

Do you want to know how the cities of tomorrow are designed and how you can be part of this change? Secure your slot for the Urban Jungle conference until the 10th of March!! and listen to new and visionary voices, engage with urban change leaders from all over Europe and share your ideas and visions on how to make our cities more sustainable and liveable.

📄 Register here: <http://bit.ly/3pmhVRX>

🌐 Check out the BUILD website for more information: <https://lnkd.in/eUMb7Y8>

The 'Urban Jungle' is waiting for you!

Registrations and more info at:
www.build-solutions.org/ecological-business/
buildconference2021@gmail.com

Are you a startup working on sustainable solutions?
Check out our competition call:
www.build-solutions.org/european-start-up-comp

Organized by: BUILD'S, WU, European Commission, Sustainable Business, CITY FACILITATORS, ECOTICA, Bio Plant+

With the collaboration of: IZALC, UNIVERSITE DE LOURAIN, CITEA

3

Like Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 95 Impressions

Organic stats ⓘ

Targeted to: All followers

95 Impressions	3 Reactions	4.21% Click-through rate
0 Comments	0 Shares	4 Clicks
7.37% Engagement rate		

Horizon 2020 : No 771738
The Research information it cont

BUILDs Online International Conference

URBAN JUNGLE | sustainable cities in the making
18-19 March 2021
Inspiration & Entrepreneurial Action

Do you want to know how the cities of tomorrow are designed and how you can be part of this change?

- GAIN EXPERTISE** Learn from those who are already in the field
- GET INSPIRED** Get to know the driving forces behind the scenes
- SHARE YOUR IDEAS** Join our action workshops to tackle current challenges
- MAKE IT HAPPEN** Connect with people and find solutions for the cities of tomorrow

Listen to new and visionary voices and engage with urban change leaders from different disciplines, countries and professions.
From students to policy makers, from startups

We are putting our spotlights on:

- Urban Design
- Nature-Based Solutions

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 3/4/2021

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11

The shift of focus in agroecology education.
The 5 core competences.
<https://lnkd.in/eXZ8vuQ>

#education #training #agroecology #actionlearning #agricultural #sustainability

1 The shift of focus in agroecology education the five core co
youtube.com

5

Like Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 131 Impressions

Organic stats ⓘ
Targeted to: All followers

131	5	0.76%
Impressions	Reactions	Click-through rate
0	0	1
Comments	Shares	Click
4.58%	Engagement rate	

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 3/8/2021

NextFood Project
285 followers
1mo

12

European Workshop on identification of strategies for improvements (WP4)

On Thursday, March 4 th , 2021, the University of Bologna team held an online European workshop in the context of Task 4.2: "Identification of strategies for improvements".

The workshop was part of a larger round of ten workshops organized by the partners of the NextFOOD project in their countries (e.g., https://lnkd.in/drBF_jA).

Those first ten workshops aimed to identify the strategies for improvement of actual education and training policies in a local/national perspective according to the EU Farm to Fork objectives.

The aim of the European workshop was to present the outcomes of those workshops and to collect feed-backs in order to develop an EU-level perspective on the topic.

In this vein, invited participants were a group of selected stakeholders aware of EU education and training policies in agri-food and forestry sectors. A final number of twenty people took part at the meeting.

A fruitful discussion was made, rich in suggestions and comments by participants.

The outcomes will be summarized and presented in Deliverable 4.2: "Report on Identification of strategies for improvements"

6

Like Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 192 Impressions

Organic stats ⓘ
Targeted to: All followers

192	6	2.6%
Impressions	Reactions	Click-through rate
0	0	5
Comments	Shares	Clicks
5.73%	Engagement rate	

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 3/10/2021

...

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13

Strengthening farm communities through education involvement. In #nextfoodproject, we know that by involving students in action-oriented, real-life projects throughout their studies, they become much better prepared for working in those same real-life environments after graduation. In our project we study processes where students collaborate with stakeholders in society (farmers, food processors, policy makers, etc.) and we see that these collaborations have mutual benefits to all involved stakeholders. Interested in learning more about Case 1: Agroecology: Action Learning in Farming and Food Systems - NextFood (nextfood-project.eu)? Read the practice abstract "Strengthening farm communities through education involvement" in the following link: <https://lnkd.in/g/f4yytG...>

#farmcommunities #actionresearch #actionlearning #agroecology

5

Like Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 107 Impressions

Hide stats ^

Organic stats

Targeted to: All followers

107 Impressions	5 Reactions	2.8% Click-through rate
0 Comments	0 Shares	3 Clicks

7.48%
Engagement rate

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738

The present Deliverable reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 3/12/2021

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3w •

14

Happy to join efforts with #DESIRA in emphasizing the need of training in order to further develop digital skills/reskilling of farmers and farmer workers, but also farm advisors/intermediaries.

#farmcommunities #nextfoodproject #actionlearning #ruraldigitalization

2

Like Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 97 Impressions

Hide stats

Organic stats

Targeted to: All followers

97	2	0%
Impressions	Reactions	Click-through rate

0	0	0
Comments	Shares	Clicks

2.06%
Engagement rate

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 3/15/2021

...

NextFood Project
285 followers
3w • 14

15

The shift of focus in agroecology education - the 5 core competencies:
📺 1 observation 🗣️
<https://lnkd.in/ebGemsK> #education #training #skills #agroecology #innovation

2 Observation

2 Observation

youtube.com

👍 3

I think... Thank you for... Well said... Very useful... Do

👍 Like 🗣️ Comment

NextFOOD Add a comment... 😊 📷

Organic impressions: 85 Impressions

Hide stats ↗️

Organic stats ⓘ

Targeted to: All followers

85 Impressions	3 Reactions	1.18% Click-through rate
0 Comments	0 Shares	1 Click

4.71%
Engagement rate

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738
The present Deliverable reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

NextFood Project
285 followers
3w • 🌐

16

▶ Involving local actors in action research

Engagement of local actors and creation of linkages with local agri-food systems is a successful element in the action-research approach developed in the MSc course in Organic Agriculture (MOA) at CIHEAM, Italy, where learners are confronted with sustainability issues affecting decisions of local actors and are involved in working out concrete solutions together with them.

Want to learn more about engagement of local actors in Case 11:

<https://lnkd.in/eRqnZEq>

#localactors #agrifoodsystems #sustainability #actionresearch #actionlearning

Case 11- Community of Practice (CoP) for Sustainable innovation in the agrifood systems

nextfood-project.eu • 1 min read

👍 6

Thanks for posting...

This will help me...

Well said...

What is... >

👍 Like 💬 Comment

Next FOOD Add a comment...

Organic impressions: 150 Impressions

Hide stats ^

Organic stats ⓘ

Targeted to: All followers

150	6	0,67%
Impressions	Reactions	Click-through rate
0	0	1
Comments	Shares	Click
4.67%		
Engagement rate		

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 3/17/2021

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17

The shift of focus in agroecology education - the core competencies participation

<https://lnkd.in/eDZW8zS>

3 Participation
youtube.com

3 Participation

youtube.com

5

Thanks for sharing...

I think this is...

Can I add...

Tha

Like

Comment

Add a comment...

Organic impressions: 134 Impressions

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Organic stats

Targeted to: All followers

134

Impressions

5

Reactions

1.49%

Click-through rate

0

Comments

1

Share

2

Clicks

5.97%

Engagement rate

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 3/19/2021

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18

digital meetings with local stakeholders and agricultural producers presenting the current stage of development of the #NextFOOD Project.

The second digital meeting was organized at 4th of March 2021 with the participation of 22 experts of the AC RCM members, such as Association of Industries of Greece (SVE), Exporters' Association of Northern Greece – SEVE, Region Central Macedonia, Chamber of Serres, Municipality of Paionia, GAIA Epixeirein, Chamber of Chalkidiki, American Farm School, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki - Department of Agriculture, Winemakers of Northern Greece (ENOAVE SA), Hellenic livestock association, Chamber of Small and medium Sized industries of Thessaloniki (VETH) and Chalkidiki Hotels Association. The direct involvement of these organizations in the promotion of NextFood results and the means to enhance the impact of the project activities at regional level were discussed during the meeting.

<https://lnkd.in/grV5sVn>

#nextfoodproject #horizon2020 #foodsystem #argifood #agroecology #farming #farm #agriscap #agritech #agrotechnology #research #innovative #sustainability

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Analytics ▾ Activity

NextFood | Innovative Science & Education for Sustainable Agriculture
nextfood-project.eu • 1 min read

7

Like

Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 236 Impressions

Organic stats

Targeted to: All followers

236

Impressions

7

Reactions

2.12%

Click-through rate

0

Comments

1

Share

5

Clicks

5.51%

Engagement rate

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 3/19/2021

NextFood Project
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2w •

19

digital meetings with local stakeholders and agricultural producers presenting the current stage of development of the NextFood Project.

Agronutritional Cooperation Region Central Macedonia/ACRCM had successfully organized two digital meetings with local stakeholders and agricultural producers in order to promote and present the current stage of development of the NextFOOD project. Specifically, AC RCM coordinated 2.5-hour meeting at 23rd of February 2021 with 15 local producers and agricultural cooperatives where the project aims, and deliverables were presented. The participants discussed the current situation of the agricultural sector and the problem they are facing due the COVID -19 situation. Their indirect involvement in the NextFOOD project activities was debated together with the president of AC RCM, Mr. Konstantinos Kiltidis

#nextfoodproject #horizon2020 #foodsystem #argifood #organicfood #agroecology #farming #farm #agriscap #agritech #agrotechnology #research #innovative #sustainability

10

Like Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 195 Impressions

Organic stats

Targeted to: All followers

195 Impressions	10 Reactions	2.05% Click-through rate
0 Comments	1 Share	4 Clicks
7.69% Engagement rate		

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 3/21/2021

NextFood Project
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2w •

20

The shift of focus in agroecology education - the core competencies

dialogue
<https://lnkd.in/eC3HQ7U>

4 Dialogue
youtube.com

4 Dialogue
youtube.com

4

What about... Thanks for sharing... Well said... This will hel

Like Comment

Add a comment...

Organic impressions: 107 Impressions

Hide stats

Organic stats

Targeted to: All followers

107 Impressions	4 Reactions	0% Click-through rate
0 Comments	0 Shares	0 Clicks
3.74% Engagement rate		

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 3/25/2021

NextFood Project
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21

Τι είναι το NextFood Project?

Το έργο αφορά ένα νέο μοντέλο παροχής γεωργικών γνώσεων με βιωματική μάθηση/action learning model, το οποίο δίνει έμφαση στη γνώση των αγροτών και στη σημασία της δημιουργίας συνεργειών μεταξύ όλων των εμπλεκομένων παραγόντων του γεωργικού τομέα, ώστε να τονιστεί η αειφορική διάσταση στην οποία πρέπει να στραφεί η αγροτική παραγωγή.

Στο πλαίσιο του έργου NEXTFOOD θα εφαρμοστούν δώδεκα case studies με σκοπό την ενσωμάτωση του action learning model στη γεωργία και την διασφάλιση της ποιότητας στην έρευνα και την εκπαίδευση, δημιουργώντας ένα νέο σύστημα αξιολόγησης των αποτελεσμάτων της έρευνας, με έμφαση στην βιωσιμότητα και την πρακτική χρησιμότητα.

#nextfoodproject #actionlearning #agriculture #CaseStudy #sustainability
<https://lnkd.in/eRRsMu9>

See translation

NextFOOD Presentation in GREEK

youtube.com

3

Like Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 64 Impressions

Organic stats

Targeted to: All followers

64	3	1.56%
Impressions	Reactions	Click-through rate

0	0	1
Comments	Shares	Click

6.25%
Engagement rate

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 3/25/2021

NextFood Project
285 followers
1w •

22

Farmers as teachers of Agroecology

During the 3-month certificate course in Agroecology at the University of Calcutta, India, target students act as farmer trainers and extension workers staying with the farmers and engaging in multiple forms of structured interaction.

Farmers provide feedback on students' performance and engagement in the learning process.

Want to learn more about students' interaction with farmers in Case 9 "Improving sustainability in farming and food systems by bringing in agroecological approach through action learning" ?

Read the following link:
<https://lnkd.in/enFbWgZ>

#agroecology #farmers #actionresearch #actionlearning

Horizon 2
lo 771738
Research
ation it co

Case 9- Improving sustainability in farming and food systems by bringing in agroecological approach through action learning

nextfood-project.eu • 1 min read

3 • 1 comment

Thanks for posting... I think... Love this... I wonder... +

Like Comment

Add a comment...

Organic impressions: 88 Impressions

Hide stats

Organic stats

Targeted to: All followers

88	3	1.14%
Impressions	Reactions	Click-through rate

1	0	1
Comment	Shares	Click

5.68%
Engagement rate

NextFood Project
285 followers
1w · 🌐

23

<https://lnkd.in/eDtAYvu>

NextFOOD PLATFORM

👍 6

👍 Like 💬 Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 104 Impressions

Hic

Organic stats ⓘ

Targeted to: All followers

104 Impressions	6 Reactions	3.85% Click-through rate
0 Comments	0 Shares	4 Clicks
9.62% Engagement rate		

NextFood Project
285 followers
6d · 🌐

24

The shift of focus in agroecology education - the 3 core competencies: reflection

https://lnkd.in/eZ6b_hC

5 Reflection
youtube.com

👍 3

5 Reflection

youtube.com

👍 3

👍 Like 💬 Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 58 Impressions

Organic stats ⓘ

Targeted to: All followers

58 Impressions	3 Reactions	1.72% Click-through rate
0 Comments	0 Shares	1 Click
6.9% Engagement rate		

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tion it contains

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 4/7/2021

...

NextFood Project
285 followers
22h •

25

Farm visit: How to open your farm to students

Didactic farm visits organized by UNISG, Italy, have mutual benefits for the students as for the farmers, and include constructive dialogue and knowledge sharing between students and farmers, practical experience, networking and building new relations.

During well-organized farm visits, farmers have the opportunity to engage young people into farming activities and to provide practical cases for learning.

Want to learn more about Case 8, follow the link:
<https://lnkd.in/eWm-ab7>

Read the practice abstract on "Farm visit: How to open your farm to students":
<https://lnkd.in/eMxJGQH>

#farmvisits #actionresearch #actionlearning

4

Like Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Organic impressions: 47 Impressions

Hide stats

Organic stats

Targeted to: All followers

47 Impressions	4 Reactions	0% Click-through rate
-------------------	----------------	--------------------------

0 Comments	0 Shares	0 Clicks
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8.51%
Engagement rate

Posted by Daphne Kapsala • 2/10/2021
• Boost unavailable

Pinned

...

26

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2mo • Edited •

Sign in to our Educational Platform:
<https://lnkd.in/d2gF5fc>

NextFOO Educational Platform

8

Like Comment

Be the first to comment on this

Video views: 149 total

Video views

Targeted to: All followers

149
Total

Organic stats

441 Impressions	8 Reactions	2.04% Click-through rate
--------------------	----------------	-----------------------------

0 Comments	2 Shares	9 Clicks
---------------	-------------	-------------

4.31%
Engagement rate

NextFOO Educational Platform

8

Like Comment

0

Ex
ain

NEXT FOOD PLATFORM:
Reporting from November 2019 to April 2021

Annex 9 NextFOOD LinkedIn posts' Statistics

Post	Impressions	Reactions	Click-through rate	Comments	Share
1	139	6	4.32%	0	1
2	149	10	1.34%	0	1
3	140	7	2.14%	0	0
4	245	7	4.49%	0	2
5	211	11	4.74%	0	2
6	242	7	4.96%	0	0
7	154	5	1.95%	0	0
8	110	3	9.09%	0	0
9	107	4	0.93%	0	0
10	95	3	4.21%	0	0
11	131	5	0.76%	0	0
12	192	6	2.60%	0	0
13	107	5	2.80%	0	0
14	97	2	0.00%	0	0
15	85	3	1.18%	0	0
16	150	6	0.67%	0	0
17	134	5	1.49%	0	1
18	236	7	2.12%	0	1
19	195	10	2.05%	0	1
20	107	4	0.00%	0	0
21	64	3	1.56%	0	0
22	88	3	1.14%	1	0
23	104	6	3.85%	0	0
24	58	3	1.72%	0	0
25	47	4	0.00%	0	0
26	441	8	2.04%	0	2

Clicks Engagement rate

6	9.35%
2	8.72%
3	7.14%
11	8.16%
10	10.90%
12	7.85%
3	5.19%
10	11.82%
1	4.67%
4	7.37%
1	4.58%
5	5.73%
3	7.48%
0	2.06%
1	4.71%
1	4.67%
2	5.97%
5	5.51%
4	7.69%
0	3.74%
1	6.25%
1	5.68%
4	9.62%
1	6.90%
0	8.51%
9	4.31%

Αυτό το γράφημα δεν είναι διαθέσιμο στη δική σας έκδοση

Εάν επεξεργαστείτε αυτό το σχήμα ή εάν αποθηκεύσετε αυτήν την εργασία σε διαφορετική μορφή αρχείου, το γράφημα θα κριθεί οριστικά.

του Excel.

τό το βιβλίο
αταστραφεί

Click-through rate for the period 20/10-13/04/2021

Engagement rate for the period 20/10-13/04/2021

NEXT FOOD PLATFORM:

Reporting from November 2019 to April 2021

Annex 10 NextFOOD Newsletter 7th Mailchimp

NextFOOD Newsletter 7th

Sent

Wed, Mar 24, 2021 14:04

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Overview	1
Opens by location	2
Subscriber activity	3
Click performance	4
Social stats	5
Advanced reports	6

NextFOOD Newsletter 7th

Sent 3/24/21 14:04

Overview

350 Recipients

Audience: NextFood project**Delivered:** Wed, Mar 24, 2021 14:04**Subject:** NextFOOD Newsletter 7th

0 Orders	\$0.00 <u>Average order revenue</u>	\$0.00 <u>Total revenue</u>
--------------------	---	---------------------------------------

101 Opened	16 Clicked	19 Bounced	1 Unsubscribed
----------------------	----------------------	----------------------	--------------------------

Successful deliveries	331 94.6%	Clicks per unique opens	15.8%
Total opens	169	Total clicks	30
Last opened	4/6/21 19:16	Last clicked	4/6/21 19:55
Forwarded	0	Abuse reports	0

NextFOOD Newsletter 7th

Sent 3/24/21 14:04

Opens by location

Country	Opens	Percent
USA	66	40.0%
Greece	30	18.2%
Sweden	17	10.3%
France	7	4.2%
Croatia	6	3.6%
India	5	3.0%
Belgium	5	3.0%
Italy	4	2.4%
Portugal	4	2.4%
Austria	3	1.8%

NextFOOD Newsletter 7th

Sent 3/24/21 14:04

Subscriber activity

24-hour performance

Opens

Clicks

Top links clicked

https://www.nextfood-project.eu/	6
https://mcusercontent.com/93f3bfd80fc2b694e962261ca/files/e9e5cec5-a0fc-4abb-9753-b4f4ac357cf3/Strengthening_farm_communities_through_education_involvement.pdf	4
https://www.nextfood-project.eu/newsletter-march-2021/	4
https://mcusercontent.com/93f3bfd80fc2b694e962261ca/files/b59cf540-e57b-4914-a3fa-71da29c5214c/New_NextFOOD_Case_Study_in_Latin_America.pdf	3
http://agromacedonia.gr/	2

Subscribers with most opens

lotta.woxblom@skogforsk.se	7
anthony.fardet@inra.fr	6
laurent.reverdy@flourmillers.eu	5
anet.rezek.jambrak@pbf.unizg.hr	6
d.kapsala@agromacedonia.gr	7

NextFOOD Newsletter 7th

Sent 3/24/21 14:04

Click performance

URL	Total	Unique
https://www.nextfood-project.eu/	6 (20.0%)	6 (22.2%)
https://mcusercontent.com/93f3bfd80fc2b694e9622...	4 (13.3%)	2 (7.4%)
https://www.nextfood-project.eu/newsletter-march-20...	4 (13.3%)	4 (14.8%)
https://mcusercontent.com/93f3bfd80fc2b694e9622...	3 (10.0%)	2 (7.4%)
http://agromacedonia.gr/	2 (6.7%)	2 (7.4%)
https://www.iseki-food.net/	2 (6.7%)	2 (7.4%)
https://www.slu.se/	2 (6.7%)	2 (7.4%)
https://www.uchile.cl/english	1 (3.3%)	1 (3.7%)
https://mcusercontent.com/93f3bfd80fc2b694e9622...	1 (3.3%)	1 (3.7%)
https://www.skogforsk.se/SFdagarna	1 (3.3%)	1 (3.7%)
https://www.nmbu.no/	1 (3.3%)	1 (3.7%)
https://nextfood-project.us19.list-manage.com/subscri...	1 (3.3%)	1 (3.7%)
http://platform.nextfood-project.eu	1 (3.3%)	1 (3.7%)
https://www.linkedin.com/company/nextfood-project/...	1 (3.3%)	1 (3.7%)
https://www.welthungerhilfe.org/	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
https://www.caluniv.ac.in/	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
https://www.instagram.com/nextfoodproject/	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
https://www.facebook.com/nextfoodinnovativescienc...	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)

URL	Total	Unique
https://www.afs.edu.gr/	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
https://twitter.com/NextFood3	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
https://mcusercontent.com/93f3bfd80fc2b694e9622...	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
https://mcusercontent.com/93f3bfd80fc2b694e9622...	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
https://mcusercontent.com/93f3bfd80fc2b694e9622...	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
https://mcusercontent.com/93f3bfd80fc2b694e9622...	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
https://mcusercontent.com/93f3bfd80fc2b694e9622...	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCEjsZeXhtM_S3kj...	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)

NextFOOD Newsletter 7th

Sent 3/24/21 14:04

Social stats

No geographic clicks have been registered yet

No campaign URL activity to report yet.

NextFOOD Newsletter 7th

Sent 3/24/21 14:04

Advanced reports

Email Domain Performance

Domain	Email	Bounces	Opens	Clicks	Unsubs
gmail.com	164 (47%)	4 (2%)	48 (30%)	8 (5%)	1 (1%)
yahoo.com	13 (4%)	0 (0%)	3 (23%)	1 (8%)	0 (0%)
pkm.gov.gr	10 (3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
hotmail.com	9 (3%)	0 (0%)	6 (67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
afs.edu.gr	8 (2%)	2 (25%)	3 (50%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)
Other	146 (42%)	13 (9%)	41 (31%)	6 (5%)	0 (0%)

NEXT FOOD PLATFORM:
Reporting from November 2019 to April 2021

Annex 11 NexfFOOD Mailchimp Report

Next FOOD

EDUCATING THE NEXT GENERATION
OF PROFESSIONALS IN THE AGRIFOOD SYSTEM

2021

Mailchimp Report

NEXT FOOD PROJECT

STATISTIC INFORMATION FOR THE PERIOD 10/20 -04/21

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738

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The partners have sent a common newsletter at 24/03/2021. It was sent to 350 mailing contacts, registered though the NEXT FOOD website. 103 of them open the newsletter.

NextFOOD Newsletter 7th

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PROJECT STATUS IN BRIEF

Welcome to the seventh edition of the NEXT FOOD Newsletter!

by Martin Melin, [NextFood](#) coordinator, [SLU](#)

A transition towards a more sustainable society will require that we think and act in fundamentally different ways. The important role of education in fostering coming generations to take ethical and responsible action with a healthy planet in mind, is emphasized by UNESCO in the report "Education for Sustainable Development Goals". In the UNESCO report, a set of cross-cutting key competencies for sustainability is highlighted, among them systems thinking (going to the roots of the problems), collaborative competency (learning together with others) and critical thinking (to question norms, practices and your own values). The report states that these are competences that cannot be taught (for example by listening to a lecture) but have to be developed by the learners themselves in action-oriented learning activities. This is in line with the educational approach of the Next food project, and you can read about some of our initiatives in the 7th Newsletter where we present the progress and some outcomes of the project. Although, it has been complicated times for project implementation, we have seen a high level of activity in Next food. These are some of the things that are going on:

- At present we are updating the [Next Food inventory of skills](#) by analyzing the results of a survey where 400+ value chain stakeholders responded. It will give us a detailed view on what skills that will be needed by various professional groups in the value chain.
- By using [methods from the field of informatics](#) we are analyzing data from EU higher

Most of the e-mails were in GMAIL accounts.

Email Domain Performance

Domain	Email	Bounces	Opens	Clicks	Unsubs
gmail.com	164 (47%)	4 (2%)	50 (31%)	8 (5%)	1 (1%)
yahoo.com	13 (4%)	0 (0%)	3 (23%)	1 (8%)	0 (0%)
pkm.gov.gr	10 (3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
hotmail.com	9 (3%)	0 (0%)	6 (67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
afs.edu.gr	8 (2%)	2 (25%)	3 (50%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)
Other	146 (42%)	13 (9%)	41 (31%)	6 (5%)	0 (0%)

The open rate is 31.1 % with about 4.8 % Click rate.

Successful deliveries	331	94.6%	Clicks per unique opens	15.5%
Total opens	173		Total clicks	30
Last opened	4/12/21 20:40		Last clicked	4/6/21 19:55
Forwarded	0		Abuse reports	0

24-hour performance

Top locations by opens

USA	68	40.2%
Greece	30	17.8%
Sweden	17	10.1%
France	8	4.7%
Croatia	7	4.1%

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 by **Martin Melin**, *NextFood* coordinator, **SLU**

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- At present we are updating the **Next Food inventory of skills** by analyzing the results of a survey where 400+ value chain stakeholders responded. It will give us a detailed view on what skills that will be needed by various professional groups in the value chain.
- By using **methods from the field of informatics** we are analyzing data from **EU higher education websites**, including course descriptions and syllabi, which will give us the possibility to identify the gaps of skills and competences in existing education within the **agri-food and forestry sector**.

Click Summary

Click Rate 16 recipients who clicked / 331 successful deliveries	4.8%
Clicks Per Unique Open 16 recipients who clicked / 103 unique opens	15.5%
View More	

Links by: Appearance order

1	nextfood-project.eu/	10.0%	>
2	slu.se/	6.7%	>
3	nextfood-project.eu/newsletter-m...	13.3%	>
4	agromacedonia.gr/	6.7%	>
5	mcusercontent.com/93f3bfd80fc2...	0.0%	>
6	afs.edu.gr/	0.0%	>
7	mcusercontent.com/93f3bfd80fc2...	0.0%	>
8	skogforsk.se/SFdagarna	3.3%	>
9	mcusercontent.com/93f3bfd80fc2...	0.0%	>
10	mcusercontent.com/93f3bfd80fc2...	0.0%	>
11	uchile.cl/english	3.3%	>
12	mcusercontent.com/93f3bfd80fc...	10.0%	>

NEXT FOOD PLATFORM:

Reporting from November 2019 to April 2021

Annex 12 NextFOOD New Templates: Leaflets & Newsletter

Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system

PASTE YOUR TITLE HERE

PASTE YOUR SECONDARY TITLE HERE

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www.nextfood-project.eu

Info@nextfood-project.eu

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